

THE MODERATING EFFECT OF FIRM FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE IN THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN BOARD DIVERSITY, BOARD MEETING AND CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY DISCLOSURE IN NON-FINANCIAL COMPANY IN NIGERIA

¹Shamsuddeen Yusuf Bugaje (Fena, Mtm, M.Sc. PhD), ²Bishir Balarabe (M.Sc. PhD in View) and ³Khalid Shariff Abdulkadir (BSc. M.Sc. PhD in View)

Department of Accounting, Federal University, Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State

Email: bugajeshamsuddeen@gmail.com; muhammadbishirbala@gmail.com;

Khalidshariff2017@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13628962>

Keywords: Financial Performance, Board diversity & Board Meeting.

Abstract: Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) is a concept of social responsibility that aims to inform the public about a company's social actions and their effects on society while also addressing the company's long-term viability (Many corporate social responsibility approaches in developing economies are based on developed-country norms and frameworks. The main purpose of this study is to investigate the moderating effects of firm financial performance relationship between board diversity, board meeting and corporate social responsibility disclosure in listed non-financial companies in particular. The sample data utilized in this study consists of 161 firms in Nigeria's listed non-financial companies throughout a ten-year period (2013-2022). Women on boards, board meetings, profitability are the variables considered as interaction variables to affect business performance. Firm size, and age are all control factors. Regression models were used to analyze the data. The findings of this study showed that Nigerian non-financial company release information based on women on boards, board make up, community characteristics, employee information, and other factors. However, the result of the joint interaction of board diversity and board meetings reveals a strong moderating effect on the relationship between board diversity and board meetings and corporate social responsibility disclosure, which is positive and statistically significant. The results presented reveals sufficient evidence that profitability are positively significant moderating effect on the relationship between BM,WOB and CSRD and therefore the null hypothesis (H01,H02) of the study is rejected. Firms should also focus on corporate social responsibility for the improvement of firm performance and internal corporate governance practices. Thus, governments and regulatory authorities should focus

Shamsuddeen Yusuf Bugaje, Bishir Balarabe and Khalid Shariff Abdulkadir

on corporate social responsibility for firms, which may reduce those industrial negative impacts on the environment.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) is a concept of social responsibility that aims to inform the public about a company's social actions and their effects on society while also addressing the company's long-term viability (Gray et al., 1997). CSR also refers to a company's commitment to contribute to long-term economic development through corporate social responsibility, which focuses on striking a balance between economic, social, and environmental considerations (Dakhli, 2021). Corporate Social Responsibility Disclosure (CSRD) is a method of disclosing information concerning company interactions with regard to the environment, employees, society, and consumer concerns. It is a method of disclosing both financial and non-financial information in a social and environmental context (Jihai et al., 2021).

Board meetings (BM); Board meetings is measured as number of meetings held by the committee within a year as used by (Samaila, 2014). BM is one of the major catalyst used by the board members and every stakeholders that come together to discuss and solve problems bedeviling the company from time to time either annually, semi-annually or mostly four times in a year for the progress of the company and

measured by the number of time to be met annually (Samaila, 2014).

Women on board (WOB); Women on board can be seen as a female entrepreneur who plays a pivotal role in the emerging economy. WOB is measured as a Proportion of females in the board used as a proxy of women as well as board diversity (Muhammad et al., 2017). Women on boards are regarded as an important dimension of corporate board characteristics that influence the extent of environmental disclosure and contribute to corporate boards by forming alliances, preparing and participating in important decisions, taking leadership roles, and being visible (Ajepe et al., 2021). However, a higher share of women on corporate boards leads to improved corporate communication, a different approach to environmental concerns, and an existing association between the level of environmental disclosure and the number of women on corporate boards (Ajepe et al., 2021). Profitability, as a moderator of firm performance, is a company's ability to earn profit or gain that would sustain the company's long-term and short-term growth; however, profitability is one of the factors that allows management to disclose CSR activity with a high degree of flexibility (Idowu, 2014); in addition, the literature on board characteristics suggests that CSR can improve profits and prove that

Advance Journal of Management, Accounting and Finance

Adv. J. Man. Acc. Fin

Volume: 9 Issue: 8,

August, 2024

ISSN: 2364 – 4219

Impact Factor: 6.93

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/ajmaf/>

almost no large public company today would want to be seen unengaged (Idowu, 2014).

Firm size as a control variable can be measured using different parameters, including sales, assets, employees, and benefits, among others. The number of employees, assets, and sales are the most frequently used. This research suggests that company size does matter in consumer response to CSR engagement and offers initial explanations for it.

Firm age as a control variable measures the time between the initial creation of a firm and the present time (in years). The research measure firm age as the time between its going public and the present time (also in years). Based on stakeholder theory, the study anticipate that older companies engage in CSR activities in larger extent and found strongly positive relationship From this point of view, older firms can engage CSR more effectively in their financial performance. Nevertheless, the research expect firm age to have a negative impact.

Despite the strategic importance of the various sectors in the industry to the economy, not much attention in CSR research is given to non-financial sector of the economy especially in Nigeria. It is on this contextual that this study is set to scrutinize Women on board, board meeting and corporate social responsibility disclosure in the presence of moderating effect of firm financial performance and the control variables with particular focus on in Nigerian non-

financial sector, in order to close the existing gap in the local literature. The main objective of this study is to ascertain the extent to which 1. To examine whether women on board, board meetings) have effects on Corporate Social Responsibility Disclosure 2. To determine whether profitability moderate the relationship between women on board, board meetings and Corporate Social Responsibility Disclosure. In order to address the research problem properly, research question has been raised to find answers to the following research questions on the moderating influence of firm financial performance and control variables on the effects of women on board, board meetings on corporate social responsibility disclosure in the Nigerian non-financial sector: 1.How does women on board, board meetings affect Corporate Social Responsibility Disclosure? 2. How does profitability moderate women on board, board meetings to influence Corporate Social Responsibility Disclosure? The study is delimited to only non- financial institutions listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange from 2013 - 2022.

2.0 REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE Overview of Nigerian Corporate Social Responsibility

Exploring the motivations for CSR in Nigeria, as well as its history and progress, from a Nigerian viewpoint, is useful. The World Business Council for Sustainable Development (WBCSD) (2006), which was reviewed in 2021, discussed CSR with

Shamsuddeen Yusuf Bugaje, Bishir Balarabe and Khalid Shariff Abdulkadir

Advance Journal of Management, Accounting and Finance

Adv. J. Man. Acc. Fin

Volume: 9 Issue: 8,

August, 2024

ISSN: 2364 – 4219

Impact Factor: 6.93

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/ajmaf/>

business and non-business stakeholders in a number of countries around the world in order to better understand local perspectives and collect different perceptions of what CSR should mean from various societies (WBCSD, 2021).

The CSR Concept and CSR Disclosure

CSR is a strategy for achieving commercial success while upholding moral standards and showing respect for people, communities, and the environment (Anissa 2021). CSR is characterized as a corporate action that significantly improves the welfare of a named social stakeholder. To the advantage of its key stakeholders, it is a corporate practice that goes above and beyond the very minimal legal requirements.

Corporate Social Responsibility Disclosure (CSR D)

The sharing of corporate social information is, in general, optional. Corporate social disclosure is a subset of social responsibility accounting that deals with providing information to the public about a company's social and environmental activities. It should be emphasized that performance evaluation is concerned with measuring and assessing corporate social involvements. It has been shown that society uses publicly available corporate social information to make different decisions, including patronizing businesses and investing in businesses (Bouaziz, 2014).

Classification of Corporate Social Responsibility Disclosure

CSR information is contained and shared in annual reports delivered to stakeholders, and it is divided into four categories: environmental, consumer-related, employee-related, and community involvement-related information (Deegan, 2002).

Environmental Disclosure. Environmental Financial, Environmental Audit, Environmental Policy, Environmental Products and Processes, Sustainability, Energy, Waste Management Programs, Emissions levels and controls, Environmental Impact Assessments, Fish-stocking programs, Energy Conservation Activities, Landscaping Activities, Environmental Financial, Environmental Audit, Environmental Policy, Environmental Products and Processes, Sustainability, Energy, Waste Management Programs, Emissions levels and controls, Environmental Impact Assessments, Environmental Impact Assessments, Environmental Impact Assessments, Environmental Impact Assessments, Environmental Impact Assessment (Eissa et al.,2021).

Community Involvement Disclosure; This category of disclosure includes any company information related to community involvement, such as charitable and political donations, support for education, public health, the arts and culture, sponsoring sporting or recreational projects, educational programs offered, plant site visits, support for local school, sports, cultural

Shamsuddeen Yusuf Bugaje, Bishir Balarabe and Khalid Shariff Abdulkadir

activities, and volunteer programs (Halil,2016).

Community Relations Disclosure ; The underlying principal of community relations is that when a company accepts its civic responsibility and takes an active interest in the well-being of its community, it gains a number of long-term benefits in terms of community support, loyalty, and general good will. Community involvement, on the other hand, improves public perception and employee morale while also encouraging teamwork, which is crucial for long-term success. It is solely concerned with how to create an enabling environment in the host community that will allow the company to carry out its operations without hindrance (Oraka et al., 2021).

Employee Disclosure; Employee data, pension data, consultation with employees, disabled employment, Value-added statements, health and safety, share ownership, equal opportunities overall description of working environment, number of employees, absentee rate, number of minorities employed, health programs offered, education/training programs, vacation information, and sa (Carrol,2013).

Consumer Disclosure; This type of disclosure covers the following topics: product and consumer safety, consumer complaints, accessibility for the disabled, and accessibility for hard-to-reach consumers. Customer service upgrades, additions/enhancements to customer service centers/hours, upgrades to customer

service programs, billing payment method improvements, product dependability improvements, stakeholder rights–related disclosures (Deegan, 2002).

Board Meetings ; Board Meetings are one of the most important catalysts used by board members and other stakeholders to convene regular meetings to discuss and address problems that plague the company from time to time, whether yearly, semi-annually, or generally four times a year for the company's success (Halil, 2016). The company secretary's first task is to compile the minutes from previous meetings and give them to the board of directors for approval at the next meeting. This should be a very straightforward procedure if the secretary takes the time to write a draft of the previous meeting's minutes soon after the previous meeting and requests the board chair to examine them (Samaila, 2014). The next step is to obtain copies of both the financial report and any committee reports. This is also an excellent opportunity to inform board members, the executive director, the CEO, and other key persons of the meeting's date, time, and location (Idowu, 2014). Before the meeting, the company secretary will confirm the meeting space's availability and double-check that any essential equipment, such as a projector, screen, and audio, teleconference, or video-conferencing equipment, is on hand (Samaila, 2014). A few weeks before the meeting, the company secretary should review a draft agenda with the board chair

Advance Journal of Management, Accounting and Finance

Adv. J. Man. Acc. Fin

Volume: 9 Issue: 8,

August, 2024

ISSN: 2364 – 4219

Impact Factor: 6.93

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/ajmaf/>

and request any changes, additions, or deletions. It's also a good idea to walk any guests or speakers through the agenda so they know where they fit into the schedule and how much time the board chair will provide them for their presentations (Hajji, 2013).

Women on Board; Women on boards, as one facet of board diversity, has attracted a large amount of attention in the literature on corporate board characteristics, with proponents of diversity arguing that diverse boards may have a greater knowledge of difficult issues than homogeneous boards (Carter et al.,2003). The inclusion of females on the board of directors may push the board to fulfill the expectations of stakeholders, making CSR implementation and disclosure more feasible. As a result, the number of females on corporate boards differs greatly from the number of firms involved in CSR (Eissa et al.,2021). Because women are more stringent and trustworthy than their male counterparts, having them on the board can improve the efficacy of board control. Their involvement in board governance can aid to avoid risky projects, as they are generally more financially risk-averse than men as most companies select women on board based on the resource to which they can provide such as prestige, skills, knowledge, and connection to external resources (Durmani, 2011).

Profitability; Profitability can be seen as the ability of a company to use its resources to generate revenues in excess of its expenses. In

other words, this is a company's capability of generating profits from its operations (Eissa et al., 2021). Profitability refers to a company's capacity to make a profit or gain that will allow it to continue to expand in the long and near term (Eissa et al., 2021). Profitability is one of the criteria that allows management to report CSR activities with a great degree of flexibility (Kabir and Mohammed, 2020). Profitability is also described as a company's capacity to provide a return on an investment based on its resources, as opposed to an alternative investment. Although a business can make a profit, this does not always imply that it is profitable (Kabir and Mohammed, 2020).

Firm size can be measured using different parameters, including sales, assets, employees, and benefits, among others. The number of employees, assets, and sales are the most frequently used. This research suggests that company size does matter in consumer response to CSR engagement and offers initial explanations for it (Durmani, 2011).

Firm age measures the time between the initial creation of a firm and the present time (in years). The research measure firm age as the time between its going public and the present time (also in years).Based on stakeholder theory, the study anticipate that older companies engage in CSR activities in larger extent and found strongly positive relationship From this point of view, older firms can engage CSR more effectively in their financial performance (Hajji, 2013).

Shamsuddeen Yusuf Bugaje, Bishir Balarabe and Khalid Shariff Abdulkadir

Board Meetings and Corporate Social Responsibility Disclosure

Every stakeholder who has been invited to attend this board meeting is expected to join the board of directors to debate significant problems affecting the company's future (Samaila, 2014). Previous research has found a substantial link between board meetings and CSR (Ajepe et al., 2021; Samaila, 2014; Halil, 2016; Mohd, 2017). At least four times a year, the committee will convene. To satisfy its CG responsibilities, the board of directors must be engaged, notably in ensuring high-quality, transparent reporting in annual reports. Boards that meet on a regular basis are more likely to carry out their responsibilities efficiently and successfully. Indirectly and directly, diligent boards are likely to improve the level of monitoring of the financial reporting process through the choice of external auditor. Regarding the audit committee's composition, as well as more effective contributions to the achievement of corporate social responsibility goals, in order to bring the host community and the company's performance together (Samaila, 2014). According to Samaila (2014), a board of directors that meets seldom may only have time to approve management plans and listen to presentations, leaving them with little time to focus on concerns such as CSR reports, earnings management, or financial statement fraud. In other words, they

discovered that CSR was strongly linked to the number of board meetings.

Women on Board and Corporate Social Responsibility Disclosure

In comparison to their male directors, Daily and Dalton (2003) believe that having women on the board might provide diverse viewpoints, experiences, and work styles. Similarly, Mohd (2017) asserted that the inclusion of women on boards might increase CSR and company reputation ratings, signaling to investors the possibility for enhanced financial performance. In a similar line, Williams (2003) notes that high numbers of women on boards and corporations' benevolent and philanthropic endeavors have a beneficial relationship, based on the findings of his study. Wang and Coffey (1992) found that the representation of women and minorities on boards of directors was positively associated to corporate transparency. In recent years, studies on women on boards have gotten a lot of attention, and several nations have passed legislation allowing women to serve on the boards of publicly traded corporations. Norway and Sweden, for example, have enforced gender quotas on the boards of directors of publicly traded corporations (Guan, 2006). In addition, the Securities and Exchange Commission of the United States has mandated that all publicly traded corporations encourage diversity in board member appointments. Women filled roughly 15% of board seats in Fortune 500 businesses in 2010, according to Durman (2011), and 9.4

percent of board seats in French enterprises. As a result, companies with more women on their boards of directors are more likely to report their CSR activity.

The Moderating Effects of Firm financial Performance

Profitability is utilized to assess business performance in terms of corporate social responsibility disclosure in this study. According to the findings, corporate board qualities are positively related to business success. Second, the study revealed that CSR is linked to company performance in a positive way. Importantly, this research shows that CSR is a critical moderator of the favorable relationship between internal corporate board qualities and business success (Eissa et al., 2021).

According to Jihai et al. (2021) there is a link between profitability and CSR disclosure, Public pressure, rather than economic pressure, influences CSR disclosure. Dakhili (2021) discovered a significant positive relationship between profitability and the extent of CSR disclosure in Malaysian non-financial firms. This could be because profitable firms have a larger profit base to cover the costs of social responsibility and more resources to devote to social activities. Because they have additional finances, more profitable companies would sponsor more comprehensive social responsibility initiatives than less profitable companies (Eissa et al., 2021).

Firm Age and CSR

The level of social responsibility actions undertaken by firms often depends on the decisions of their managers and the value

orientation of the entrepreneur. Moreover, the younger a firm is, the less likely it is that it gets involved in CSR. This is the study's main assumption, young ventures display a weaker propensity for CSR actions. However, age is not a determining factor of CSR. Although, in the literature, there is no clear consensus regarding whether there is a different model of implementation of CSR related practices in developing and transitional countries.

Firm size and CSR

This research suggests that firm size does matter in consumer response to CSR engagement and offers initial explanations for it. Implications and suggestions for future research are provided. Is CSR only for large companies. Although CSR programs have generally been most common among large corporations, small businesses also participate in CSR through smaller-scale programs, such as donating to local charities and sponsoring local events. Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) allows businesses large and small to enact positive change? It's when companies choose to do what's right not only for their bottom line but also to build customer trust.

Empirical Review

Various researches on the topic of corporate social responsibility disclosure and its link to corporate board characteristics have been conducted (Anissa,2021;Dakhli,2021; Onipe,2021;Oraka et al.,2020;Iramani and Abdul,2018; Halil, 2016; Muhammad et al., 2017; Mohd, 2017; Belal, 2000: Idowu, 2014) explores CSR in the annual reports of Nigerian enterprises listed on the Nigerian stock market

Advance Journal of Management, Accounting and Finance

Adv. J. Man. Acc. Fin

Volume: 9 Issue: 8,

August, 2024

ISSN: 2364 – 4219

Impact Factor: 6.93

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/ajmaf/>

for the years 1998-2021. The study examines the overall patterns of CSR in Nigeria and developed nations and finds that CSR in Nigerian enterprises is lower, although reporting patterns are similar. Employee-related information was dominant in both nations, followed by environmental and community information, and finally customer information, which explains why some Nigerian companies provide CSR data while others do not. In other words, the study is looking at the factors that influence Nigerian companies' decision to publish CSR data in their annual reports.

Kurawa and Abdulrahman (2014) investigate the impact of corporate board features on corporate social responsibility in the Nigerian petroleum marketing business, focusing on a sample of five companies from 2002 to 2011. The findings found that management equity ownership and other factors such as board size, board composition, and CEO duality were positively correlated with corporate social responsibility actions in the Nigerian petroleum business. Gideon et al. (2021), in a similar vein, investigates the impact of company board and financial features on the degree of corporate social responsibility disclosures. The study's findings revealed that board commitment to CSR and profitability were found to be positively related with the extent of CSR disclosure, while financial leverage was negatively related to the extent of CSR disclosure. The study was conducted outside Nigeria and time period

covered was one year which is seen inadequate to give valid result.

In a similar vein, Haji (2013) performed a research on corporate social responsibility over time, which included a sample of 85 businesses listed on Bursa Malaysia over a period of time (2009 - 2013). A Multiple Regression Analysis was employed, as well as descriptive statistics. Managerial ownership, government ownership, and firm size were shown to be significant in influencing both the extent and quality of CSR disclosures, according to the research.

To put it another way, Ali and Atan (2013) investigate the link between corporate board characteristics and corporate social responsibility disclosure. For the year 2013, 120 organizations were sampled, and the link was tested using a Multiple Regression Analysis and descriptive statistics. The findings revealed that board size, board independence, and ownership concentration all had a substantial impact on CSR disclosure. The control factors, on the other hand, had no meaningful relationship with the degree of CSR disclosures. The notion of social contract influence, which states that the power of expertise encourages compliance, supports this thesis.

Certain variables have been shown in the literature to have a combined effect on the amount of disclosure. According to certain research, there is a link between a company's profitability and its corporate social responsibility spending. Jihai et al. (2021);

Shamsuddeen Yusuf Bugaje, Bishir Balarabe and Khalid Shariff Abdulkadir

Advance Journal of Management, Accounting and Finance

Adv. J. Man. Acc. Fin

Volume: 9 Issue: 8,

August, 2024

ISSN: 2364 – 4219

Impact Factor: 6.93

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/ajmaf/>

Comier et al. (2010) investigated the influence of business size, BC, and BS on corporate social responsibility in Malaysia and discovered a favorable impact on corporate social and environmental disclosure.

Onipe (2021) studied how firm size confounds the relationship between corporate social performance and firm financial performance. This study examines the integration of three meta-analyses of more than two decades of research on (1) CSP and FFP, (2) firm size and CSP and (3) firm size and FFP into one path-analytic model. The present study does not confirm size as a third factor which would confound the relationship between CSP and FFP.

Theoretical Framework

Legitimacy Theory (LT)

According to Deegan (2002), LT is a contract between a corporation and society, similar to a principal-agent relationship, to satisfy societal expectations. LT broadens the principal-agent relationship to benefit a variety of stakeholders, and this concept broadens the functions of corporate board features. As a result, in order to retain their credibility, managers are eager to provide their CSR efforts and other relevant information.

Legitimacy theory, according to Deegan (2002) indicates that organizations must guarantee that their actions are carried out within the framework (bounds and norms) of the society in which they operate. In the CSR literature, the legitimacy hypothesis is widely used to describe

the reasons for CSR. The notion is founded on the concept of a social contract, which confines an organization's operations within the parameters established by society (Gray et al., 1997).

Social Contract Theory

The social contract theory has been proposed as a theoretical foundation for explaining firms' contemporary practice of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR). Similarly, the social compact notion has been employed to support human rights since the 17th century. The notion, which is opposed to the agency theory since it supports the idea of the human right, was the cornerstone of the constitution/legal framework of many western governments, starting with England, the United States, and France. Business ethicists and philosophers have attempted to develop and examine corporate social responsibility from the standpoint of the social contract without tying it to human rights or the political social contract (Deegan, 1999). According to the social contract theory, individuals live together in society on the terms of an agreement that creates moral and political standards of conduct. Some individuals think that if we live under a social compact, we may behave morally because we choose to, rather than because a divine power forces us to (Belal, 2000). The social contract theory's primary concept is how to tie a company to society. This is the point at which businesses' ethical or moral responsibilities are raised. The current tendency

Shamsuddeen Yusuf Bugaje, Bishir Balarabe and Khalid Shariff Abdulkadir

in the understanding of CSR is to recognize a set of moral and ethical rights that are not governed by legislation. According to this view, businesses must act responsibly not just because it is the law, but also because it is the right thing to do (Idowu, 2014).

3.0 METHODOLOGY

A correlational research design was adopted due to the fact that the study measures relationship between women on board, board meeting on CSR and moderated financial performance of listed non-financial firm in Nigeria from 2013 - 2022. The research covers the twenty-two (120) non-financial firms listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE) as at 31st December, 2022. Therefore, 62 (sixty two) firms with 120 years financial statements covering the time period of 2013 to 2022 were selected based on access to their annual reports and accounts. The study used secondary data extracted from published annual reports and accounts of the sampled firms and the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE) fact book for the period of 10 years spanning from 2013 - 2022. The variables of the study consist of dependent variable which is CSR financial performance measured by CSRDI. The independent variables; WOB, BM. Method of Data Analysis Panel data is data that involves measurements of many individual units over a period of time, i.e.; the same cross-sectional unit is surveyed over time. With the aid of STATA 12, the study employed the panel regression method

to establish the relationship between Women on board, board meeting on CSR non-financial firm in Nigeria.

Model specification

The statistical technique which includes a linear regression was adapted with some modification from previous studies Deegan (2002); Bello (2012); Halil (2016); Onipe, (2021), to examine the relationship between the dependent and the independent variables in this study, and also to measure the relationship with the moderating variables and four (2) models were used in the study.

$$CSR = \beta_0 + \beta_1 (FS) + \beta_2 (AGE) + \beta_3 (WOB) + \beta_4 (BM) + \epsilon \text{ ----- (1)}$$

The results of the estimate of Model 1 was used to validate Hypothesis (H01) on the main effects formulated in chapter one.

$$CSR = \beta_0 + \beta_1 (FS) + \beta_2 (AGE) + \beta_3 (WOB) + \beta_4 (BM) + \beta_5 (PROF) + \beta_6 (WOB*PROF) + \beta_7 (BM*PROF) + \epsilon \text{ ----- (ii)}$$

The results of the estimate of Model 2 was used to validate Hypothesis (H02) on the moderating effects of profitability formulated in chapter one. Where:

CSR is corporate social responsibility disclosure

Bo ---- β_n is intercept

BM is board meetings

WOB is Women on board

PROF is profitability as moderating variable

FS is firm size as control variables

4.0 DATA PRESENTATION AND RESULT DISCUSSION

Age is the age of the firm after listing
 ϵ is the error term.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of the Variables

Variables	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
Corporate Social Responsibility Disclosure	0.87	0.07	0.47	1.00
Women On Board	1.37	0.81	0.00	5.00
Board Meetings	3.37	1.38	1	7
Firm size	6.38	826	3.23	7.90
Firm age	23.60	12.1	1	49
Prof (Return On Asset)	0.19	0.29	-0.37	5.61

Source: STATA Output 12.0 based on data in Appendix A

In Table 1. On the average (3-4) board meetings were held by the board members of the sampled companies in a financial year. This indicates that members of the board met every three - four month to discuss matters concerning the companies. The standard deviation is 0.48 which indicates low dispersion in the meeting held by the board members as shows by a minimum meeting of 3 times and maximum meeting of 7 times in a year among the companies.

Women on board have a mean of (1.4) with a minimum of (0) and a maximum of (5) respectively. The standard deviation of (0.80) indicates little dispersion among the sampled companies. Some companies do not even have women participants on board.

Age of the firm, the mean Age is 23.60, showing that on average the sampled companies are 23 years and a minimum of just 1 year and a maximum of 49 years showing that the youngest company is just 1 year and the oldest is about

49years for as at 2019. The standard deviation of 12.11 from the mean is not high. Firm size has a mean of 6.38 with minimum and maximum values of 3.23 and 7.90 respectively. The standard deviation of 0.83 suggests a considerable level of dispersion in firm size during the period under review.

The mean return on assets (Prof) is about (0.19) indicating that the average profit earned by the sampled companies is (0.19) with a maximum loss of (-34) and maximum profit of about (56). The standard deviation of (0.29) which indicates no significant dispersion among the sampled companies with regards to return on assets.

Regression Results

The relationships between the main independent variables and the dependent variable and the extent to which the relationships are moderated in the presence of profitability were determined statistically using regression analysis. The statistical analyses were carried out in a step

process, as recommended by (Halil, 2016), and were done in a number of studies including (Oraka et al., 2020; Anissa, 2021; Belal, 2000; Alabede, 2012). The results of the analyses are shown in Table 6. The findings of multiple

regressions for the Main effect in model 1, the Interacting Effect of profitability in model 2, as well as their interpretation of regression results are presented in Table 6.

Table 2 Regressions Result

Variables	Model 1	Model 2
Constant	1.3805*** (8.17)	1.3478*** (7.88)
FS	-.0124 (-1.53)	-.0124 (-1.53)
AGE	.0012 (1.47)	.0018** (2.07)
WOB	.0221** (1.98)	-.0435 (-1.19)
BM	-.0164 (0.82)	-.0016 (-0.05)
PROF		.0288*** (3.14)
WOB*PROF		-.0128 (-0.62)
BM*PROF		.0320** (-2.22)
Obs	620	620
Adjusted R2	0.0511	0.0589
Rho	.6651	.6516
P value	0.0007	0.0008
F`value	3.28	3.85
Sig	0542	.0541

Source: STATA Output 12.0 based on data in Appendix B. NOTE:

***, ** and * indicate 1% and 5% and 10% significant levels respectively; the t-value is presented in bracket in parenthesis while the other figures represent the coefficient.

Table 2 Model 1 presents the regression result of the dependent variable (CSRD) and (board meeting, women on board) The regression results reveal the cumulative Adjusted R² (0.0511) which is the multiple coefficient of determination gives the proportion or percentage of the total variation in the dependent variable as explained by the explanatory and control variables jointly. On the contribution of each variable, two variables made a significant contribution to model 1, while the contributions of other variables were marginal. Among the variables that made significant contributions, are (BM, FS) which indicate statistically significant at 1% in Model 1, while WOB indicates statistically significant at 5%. However, AGE had positive insignificant relationship with the dependent variables.

The result of Model 2 in Table 2 indicates the interaction of profitability with the independent variables in relationship with the dependent variables. First, the beta values of model 1 the main effect variables shown some improvements as FS, BM and PROF are significant at 1%, while AGE is significant at 5%. On the other hand, the statistic coefficient in Table 6 shows that profitability moderated the relationship between BM and CSRD (BM*PROF) at 5% level of significant while the interactions of (WOB*PROF) failed to significantly moderate the connection between WOB as well BM and CSRD.

The hypotheses developed on the relationship between the independent variables and dependent variables as well as the moderating effects of Profitability.

Women on Board and Corporate Social Responsibility Disclosure

The coefficient result in Model 1 shows that Women on Board are positively and significantly (P> 0.01) related to Corporate Social Responsibility Disclosure. Hence; the results rejected hypothesis two (H01) which states that Women on Board has no significant impact on Corporate Social Responsibility Disclosure.

Board Meeting and Corporate Social Responsibility Disclosure

The result of Model 1 provides evidence suggesting that the link between board meeting (BM) and corporate social responsibility disclosure (CSRD) are insignificant. Therefore, H01 which predicts that board meeting has no significant impact on corporate social responsibility disclosure s accepted.

i Effect of Profitability on Women on Board and Corporate Social Responsibility Disclosure.

The result in Table 2 reveals that the profitability had negative insignificant interacting effect on the relationship between WOB and Corporate Social Responsibility Disclosure. Therefore, null hypothesis (H02) which predicts that Profitability has no significant moderating effect on relationship between Women on Board and

Corporate Social Responsibility Disclosure is accepted.

Effect of Profitability on Board Meeting and Corporate Social Responsibility Disclosure. The result in Table 2 reveals that the profitability had positive significant interacting effect on the relationship between Board meeting and Corporate Social Responsibility Disclosure. Therefore, null hypothesis (H02) which predicts that Profitability has no significant moderating effect on relationship between Board Meeting and Corporate Social Responsibility Disclosure is rejected.

Discussion of Results

The result in the main effect proved that women on board are one of the major determinants of corporate social responsibility disclosure of information as women are naturally philanthropic in nature and convince other male board members for CSR activities. The result proved that the presence of females in the board of directors may compel the board to meet the stakeholders expectations, thus the execution of CSR and its disclosure is more viable. Thus, the number of females in the boards is significantly different with respect to the involvement of companies in CSR. However, an increased proportion of women on board lead to better corporate communication, take a different approach to environmental issues, extant relationship between the extent of disclosure related to environmental issues and the number

of women members on the corporate board, this finding is consistent with the findings of (Gideon et al.,2019;Alsaeed, 2006; Samaila, 2014). However, social contract theory predicts that a firm having the presence of women as board members encourages the management to disclose more information on CSR activities in order to attract more investors as women are philanthropic in nature.

The statistical evidence from this study proved that a significant perception of Women on board is considered as an important dimension of corporate board characteristics that influence the extent of environmental disclosure and make contributions on corporate boards by creating alliances, preparation and involvement, taking part in important decisions, taking leadership roles and being visible. Women on board as one of the aspect of board diversity gained a significant importance in corporate board characteristics literature, and advocates of diversity, diverse boards may have better understanding of complex issues as compared to homogenous board, this findings are in consistent with the previous studies such as (Eissa et al., 2021; Babatunde, 2020; Gideon et al., 2019; Halil, 2016). The descriptive statistics on the data of this study provide evidence the average (3-4) board meetings were held by the board members of the sampled companies in a financial year. This indicates that members of the board met every three - four month to discuss matters concerning the companies. The standard

Advance Journal of Management, Accounting and Finance

Adv. J. Man. Acc. Fin

Volume: 9 Issue: 8,

August, 2024

ISSN: 2364 – 4219

Impact Factor: 6.93

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/ajmaf/>

deviation is 0.48 which indicates low dispersion in the meeting held by the board members as shows by a minimum meeting of 3 times and maximum meeting of 7 times in a year among the companies. However, the regression analysis as hypothesized reveals that board meeting has no significant impact on disclosure of social responsibility information. In this board meeting, every stakeholder who is a member by invitation is expected to come together with the board of directors to discuss important issues of the company for the progress of the company. Empirically, previous studies show that board meetings have a positive relationship with CSRD which counter the result of this study (Halil, 2016 and Mohd, 2017). The evidence from this study proved a very low perception to be effective on board meeting which shows positively significant relationship with corporate social responsibility disclosure.

Moderating Effects of Profitability

The regression analysis as hypothesized WOB*PROF reveals that Profitability was introduced as moderator into model 2. However, the moderating effect of profitability on the relationship between women on board and CSRD. The result in Table 6 reveals that the profitability had negative insignificant moderating effect on the relationship between WOB*PROF on CSRD. This result proved that the moderating effect of profitability on the relationship between the variables were weak. This finding is consistent with the findings of

previous disclosure studies (Haniffa and Cooke 2002 and Ibrahim, 2018). However, it contradicts the findings of (Jihai et al., 2021; Halil, 2016) who reported a significant interaction between WOB*PROF in relation with CSR disclosure.

The evidence from this study proved a very low perception to be effective on the moderating interactions of women on board and CSRD which shows negatively insignificant relationship with corporate social responsibility disclosure and this proved the negative relationship in the second moderator to answer part of the second research question H02A.

The regression analysis as hypothesized (BM*PROF) reveals Profitability was introduced as moderator into model 2. The result shows that frequent meetings improve level of profitability in terms of revenue realization which has a direct relationship in disclosure of information of CSR activities. The results presented reveals sufficient evidence that profitability has significant effect in moderating the impact on the relationship between BM and CSRD. The result reveals that board meeting is positively and significantly associated with corporate social responsibility disclosure. This implies that as the number of meetings increases the extent of corporate social responsibility disclosure increase. This provides evidence to the users of accounting information that corporate social responsibility information increases as the number of meeting held by board members increases. Therefore users

Shamsuddeen Yusuf Bugaje, Bishir Balarabe and Khalid Shariff Abdulkadir

should invest in a company that frequently held board meetings. This finding is consistent with the findings of previous disclosure studies (Jepe et al., 2021; Jihai et al., 2021; Haniffa and Cooke 2002). However, it contradicts the findings of (Deegan, 2002), who reported an insignificant interaction between BM*PROF in relation with CSR disclosure.

5.0 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

5.1 Conclusion

In a nutshell, the main focus of the study is the moderation of independent variables on the relationship between board characteristics and CSRD with Profitability and research and development as moderators of firm performance of the listed non-financial institutions in Nigeria. In line with the objective, the study concludes that corporate board mechanisms constrain the CSRD of the listed non-financial institutions in Nigeria. (WOB) is seen to have a positive association with the level of corporate social responsibility disclosure. While (BM) is negatively insignificant relationship with CSRD in the Nigerian listed non-financial firms.

5.2 Recommendations

Following the findings and conclusions drawn, the following recommendations are deemed pertinent: 1. the finding of this study shows board meetings has significant relationship in joint moderating effect and prove the importance meetings, however, FRCN and SEC should make it mandatory for companies to give a detailed

disclosure on CSRD. In addition, necessary steps should be taken for mandatory compliance with the code of CG in disclosing CSR activities of non-financial companies and should disclose not only the number of meetings but also a highlight of what transpired during the meetings on issues that affects CSR disclosure particularly.

2. On a final note, the outcomes of this study have various suggestions for policymakers, shareholders, owners, investors, institutes, and governments. This study recommended the role of corporate social responsibility to control and monitor internal corporate board characteristics. Firms should abide by the guidance of regulatory bodies for the improvement of corporate board characteristics and social practices. Firms should identify and implement the proper actors of corporate social responsibility disclosure for the improvement of firm performance. Firms should also focus on corporate social responsibility for the improvement of firm performance and internal corporate governance practices. Thus, governments and regulatory authorities should focus on corporate social responsibility for firms, which may reduce those industrial negative impacts on the environment.

Frontier for Further Research

This study focuses on disclosures, corporate governance and measure of firm performance based on the information in the annual reports of firms although it is known that firms utilize other mass communication mechanisms. Hence, future research may consider other media for

Advance Journal of Management, Accounting and Finance

Adv. J. Man. Acc. Fin

Volume: 9 Issue: 8,

August, 2024

ISSN: 2364 – 4219

Impact Factor: 6.93

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/ajmaf/>

disclosure such as the firms' stand-alone reporting, in-house magazines, newspapers, and web-sites, the findings should be interpreted with wariness, given that this study has only considered the evaluation for ten years. For any longitudinal study for future research in this area, it would be necessary to extend the number of periods studied under the evaluation of recent legal requirements, with the global pandemic interruption in business and is highly recommended that future studies should also collect primary data through interviews.

REFERENCE

Ajepe A. O., Samuel E. A., Lateef O. M. (2021) Board Characteristics and Sustainability Reporting of Listed Non-Financial Firms in Nigeria <http://www.sciencepublishinggroup.com/j/jfa> doi: 10.11648/j.jfa.20210905.11 ISSN: 2330-7331

Aiken L.S... And West S.G. (1991) multiple regressions. Testing and interpreting interactions. Newbury Park, CA: Sage.

Aguinis H., and Gottfredson R. (2010) Best-practice recommendation for estimating interaction effects using moderated multiple regression. Journal of Organizational Behaviour.

Alabede J.O., Ariffin Z.Z. and Idris M. (2011a) Individual taxpayers' attitude and

compliance behaviour in Nigeria: The moderating role of financial condition and risk preference. Journal of Accounting and Taxation

Alexander J. W. (2012) Interaction between corporate social responsibility disclosure and profitability of Indonesian firms. International annual symposium on sustainability science and management, 373-380.

Ali M. A., and Attan R. H. (2013) The relationship between corporate govaernance and corporate social responsibility disclosure: A case of Malaysian sustainability companies and global sustainability companies. South East Asia journal of contemporary business, economics and Law, 1(3), 39-48.

Anissa D. (2021) The Moderating Role of Corporate Social Responsibility in the Association of Internal Corporate Governance and Profitability; Evidence from Pakistan International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health. 18(11)

Babatunde D. A., Folorunsho M. A., (2020) Board Characteristics and Firm's Financial Performance in Nigeria Unilorin working paper/05/2020 pg.1-2.

Shamsuddeen Yusuf Bugaje, Bishir Balarabe and Khalid Shariff Abdulkadir

Advance Journal of Management, Accounting and Finance

Adv. J. Man. Acc. Fin

Volume: 9 Issue: 8,

August, 2024

ISSN: 2364 – 4219

Impact Factor: 6.93

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/ajmaf/>

- Belal A. (2000) Environmental reporting in developing countries: empirical evidence from Bangladesh. *Eco-management and auditing journal*, 6-12.
- Bello M. M. (2012). Corporate Social Responsibility Disclosure and Financial Performance of Listed firms in downstream sector of the Nigerian Petroleum Industry.
- Bouaziz M. Z. (2014) Corporate governance and voluntary financial disclosure by Canadian listed firms. *Management review*, 9(1).
- Brown N., and Deegan C. (1999) The public disclosure of environmental performance information: A dual test of medial agenda setting theory and legitimacy. *Accounting and business research*, 29(1), 21-41.
- Carrol S. A. (2013) The business case for corporate social responsibility: A review of concept and practice. *international journal of management review*;12, 59-73.
- Coffey B. S., and Wang J. (1998) Board diversity and managerial control as predictors of corporate social performance. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 17(14), 1595-1603.
- Comier D., Ledoux M. J., and Magnan M. (2010) The information contribution of social environmental disclosure for investors.
- Dakhli A. (2021) The impact of ownership structure on corporate social responsibility: the moderating role of financial performance. *Society and Business Review*, Vol. 16 No. 4, pp. 562-591. <https://doi.org/10.1108/SBR-01-2021-0013>
- Daily C. M., and Dalton D. R. (2003) Women in the board room: A business imperative. *Journal of Business Strategy*, 24(5), 8-9.
- Deegan C. (2002) The Legitimizing Effect of Social and Environmental disclosures as theoretical foundation. *Accounting, Auditing and Accountability Journal*, 13(3), 281-310.
- Durmani S. (2011) Board diversity and firm performance: The Indonesian evidence. *Corporate ownership and control*, 9(1), 524-539.
- Eissa A. A, Ebrahim M. A., Mosab I. T. , Amgad S.D. K.(2021) The influence of corporate governance characteristics on profitability of Indian firms: An empirical investigation of firms listed on Bombay Stock Exchange .DOI [http://dx.doi.org/10.21511/imfi.18\(1\).20](http://dx.doi.org/10.21511/imfi.18(1).20)

Shamsuddeen Yusuf Bugaje, Bishir Balarabe and Khalid Shariff Abdulkadir

Advance Journal of Management, Accounting and Finance

Adv. J. Man. Acc. Fin

Volume: 9 Issue: 8,

August, 2024

ISSN: 2364 – 4219

Impact Factor: 6.93

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/ajmaf/>

21.10 Volume 18 2021, Issue #1, pp. 114-125

Esa E., and Mohd G. N. (2012) Corporate social responsibility and corporate governance in Malaysian government linked companies. *Corporate Governance*, 12(3), 292-305.

Gideon T. A., Odunayo O., Bamikole S. F. (2019) Corporate governance and financial performance: an empirical analysis of selected multinational firms in Nigeria. doi: [http://dx.doi.org/10.21511/ppm.17\(1\).2019.02](http://dx.doi.org/10.21511/ppm.17(1).2019.02)

Gray R., Dey C., Owen D., Evans R., and Zadek, S. (1997) struggling with the praxis of corporate social accounting. *Accounting, Auditing and Accountability Journal*, 10(3), 325-364.

Gray R., Javad, M., Power, D. M., and Sinclair, C. (2001) Social and environmental disclosure and corporate characteristics: A research note and extension. *Journal of Business Finance and Accounting*, 28(3), 327-356.

Guan Y. (2006) The relationship between board of directors and corporate social responsibility: Study on Malaysian public

listed companies. Unpublished M. sc thesis, Sains Malaysia.

Haji A. A. (2013) Corporate Social Responsibility Disclosure Overtime: Evidence from Malaysia. *Managerial Auditing Journal*, 28(7), 647-676.

Halil E. (2016) Relationship between board characteristics and environmental disclosure: evidence from Turkish listed companies. *Associate professor Yildis Technical university journal*, 21-45.

Haniffa R. M., and Cooke, T. E. (2002) Culture, corporate governance and disclosure in Malaysian corporations. *Abacus*, 38(3), 317-349.

Haniffa, R. M., and Cooke, T. E. (2005) the Impact of Culture and Governance on Corporate Reporting. *Journal of Accounting and Public Policy*, 24(5), 391-430.

Ibrahim A.A. (2018) Corporate Governance and Real Earnings Management in Nigerian Financial Institutions: The Moderating Effect of Independent Directors Universiti Utara Malaysia Tunku Puteri Intan Safinaz School of Accountancy Universiti Utara Malaysia Unpublished Thesis

Shamsuddeen Yusuf Bugaje, Bishir Balarabe and Khalid Shariff Abdulkadir

Advance Journal of Management, Accounting and Finance

Adv. J. Man. Acc. Fin

Volume: 9 Issue: 8,

August, 2024

ISSN: 2364 – 4219

Impact Factor: 6.93

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/ajmaf/>

Idowu A. (2014) Corporate social responsibility in Nigerian Banking industry: when will the lip-of service games end? dept of management and accounting journal ISSN 2222-1700 ladke university, ogbomoso, Nigeria, 2222-2855 vol.5 No.22.

Iramani M. M. , Abdul M. (2018) Positive contribution of the good corporate governance rating to stability and performance: evidence from Indonesia doi: [http://dx.doi.org/10.21511/ppm.16\(2\)](http://dx.doi.org/10.21511/ppm.16(2)).

Jihai L.S., Ahmad J., Rashid L. T. J. and Tze San O. (2021) The Moderating Role of Corporate Social Responsibility in the Association of Internal Corporate Governance and Profitability; Evidence from Pakistan. doi: 10.3390/ijerph18115830 PMID: 34071620 Int J Environ Res Public Health.18(11): 5830.

Kabir T. H., and Mohammed I. (2020) The moderating effect of corporate governance on the relationship between corporate social responsibility and financial performance of listed non-financial services companies in Nigeria International Journal of Accounting and Finance (IJAF) Vol.9, No.1, March 2020

Kurawa J. M., and Abdulrahman S. (2014) Effect of Corporate Governance on Corporate Social Responsibility of Listed Firms in the Nigerian Petroleum Marketing Industry. Proceedings of International Conference on Humanities, Science and Sustainable Development, 5(2), 27-35.

Mohd R. B. ((2017) The Effect of Board Characteristics on Corporate Social Responsibility (Csr) Disclosure Politeknik Sultan Abdul Halim Mu'adzam Shah. journal of finance, 2-25.

Muhammad A. N., Salman R., Ramiz U.R., Amir I., Fizzah M. (2017) Impact Of Board Characteristics On Corporate Social Responsibility Disclosure iaotong University, China The Journal of Applied Business Research – July/August 2017 Volume 33, Number 4

Onipe A. Y., James A. (2021) Board of directors and corporate social responsibility reporting of quoted companies in Nigeria journal of Accounting and finance DOI: 10.32602/jafas.2021.011

Oraka A. O., Francis C.E., Ardi G., (2021) The Influence of Corporate Board Attributes on Voluntary Social Disclosure of Selected Quoted Manufacturing Firms in Nigeria. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.32456/v1i1.7>

Shamsuddeen Yusuf Bugaje, Bishir Balarabe and Khalid Shariff Abdulkadir

Advance Journal of Management, Accounting and Finance

Adv. J. Man. Acc. Fin

Volume: 9 Issue: 8,

August, 2024

ISSN: 2364 – 4219

Impact Factor: 6.93

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/ajmaf/>

Samaila I. A. (2014) Corporate Governance and Financial Reporting Quality in the Nigerian Non-financial Industry. (Unpublished Doctoral Thesis) Bayero University, Kano-Nigeria.

Williams R. J. (2003) Women on corporate boards of directors and their influence on corporate philanthropy. Journal of Business Ethics, 42(1), 1-10.

Shamsuddeen Yusuf Bugaje, Bishir Balarabe and Khalid Shariff Abdulkadir